

ҚИШЛОҚ ХЎЖАЛИГИДАГИ РИСКЛАРНИ СУГУРТАЛАШНИНГ ДОЛЗАРБ МАСАЛАЛАРИ ХУСУСИДА

Мирзаев Фуркат Рахматович

Совместный Белорусско Узбекский межотраслевой институт прикладных технических
квалификаций

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Аннотация. Мақолада қишлоқ хўжалигидаги институционал ўзгаришлар шароитида давлат кўмаги асосида рискларни суғурталаш методологиясига янгича ёндошувнинг зарурлиги, асосий йўналишлари тадқиқ этилган. Қишлоқ хўжалигидаги рискларни бошқаришда суғурта тизимининг устунликлари ҳамда ўзига хос хусусиятлари илмий асослаб берилган. Ўзбекистон Республикаси қишлоқ хўжалигида уни қўллаш имкониятлари тадқиқ этилган ҳамда тавсиялар ишлаб чиқилган.

Калим сўзлар: қишлоқ хўжалиги, фермер хўжалиги, хатарлар, зарар, суғурта, агросуғурта, суғурта маҳсулотлари, хатарларни бошқариш, кредит, биржа, хеджирлаш, шартнома.

Аннотация. В статье были исследованы необходимость, основные направления нового подхода к методологии страхования рисков на основе государственной помощи в условиях институциональных преобразований в сельском хозяйстве. Показаны преимущества и особенности системы страхования при управлении сельскохозяйственными рисками. Изучены возможности и разработаны рекомендации по использованию их в сельском хозяйстве Республики Узбекистан.

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство, фермерское хозяйство, риски, убытки, страхование, агрострахование, страховые продукты, риск-менеджмент, кредит, биржа, хеджирование, договор.

Abstract. In the context of institutional changes in agriculture, the need for a new approach to the methodology of risk insurance based on state support, the main directions are researched. Advantages and specific features of the insurance system in agricultural risk management are scientifically justified. Possibilities of its application in agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan were studied and recommendations were developed.

Key words: agriculture, farm, risks, loss, insurance, agroinsurance, insurance products, risk management, credit, exchange, hedging, contract.

Introduction

In the years of independence, alongside other sectors of the economy, significant measures were implemented in the agricultural system aimed at transforming forms of ownership, creating a sense of land ownership among farmers, and establishing market infrastructure to support the system. These measures were aimed at improving the living standards of the rural population, addressing unemployment, and ensuring the supply of high-quality agricultural products to domestic and foreign markets.

Under the current conditions, institutional changes in the agricultural sector and measures to align it with contemporary demands are being consistently implemented. These measures aim to ensure that major producers of agricultural products occupy a worthy place in the global market

and contribute to food security. In this regard, during 2017–2021, the Strategy for Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasized reducing the areas sown with cotton and cereals, cultivating potatoes, vegetables, fodder, and oilseed crops on freed lands, establishing new intensive orchards and vineyards, creating favorable conditions for the development and promotion of multi-sectoral farming enterprises, establishing agro-industrial enterprises specialized in deep processing of agricultural products, and expanding modern market services based on agrochemicals, finance, and other advanced technologies.

The development of a comprehensive socio-economic development concept for Uzbekistan by 2030 is based on the 2017–2021 Strategy for Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development, as well as government decisions aimed at reforming all aspects of financial and economic relations, enhancing the economic potential of sectors and regions, and addressing social issues. The need for this concept arises from the necessity to resolve existing socio-economic problems, risks, and threats that limit the sustainable development of the economy in the long term, to define the objectives and priorities of transitioning to sustainable economic and social development, and to improve the population’s standard of living.

Implementing institutional reforms that create a favorable environment for the sustainable development trajectory of the national economy is a key condition for achieving an effective economic system in agriculture. Such a system should ensure food security through market mechanisms, liberalize resource allocation and pricing in agriculture, and implement effective land-use mechanisms.

High dependence on natural climatic conditions necessitates extensive use of insurance and insurance systems to manage risks in agricultural production. Insurance allows effective management of risks associated with the use of new technologies, credit resources, and the sale of agricultural products through exchange systems (spot, forward, futures). High-quality insurance services and related government programs enable financial stability for agricultural producers and reduce state budget expenditures aimed at supporting the agricultural sector.

In Uzbekistan, despite institutional changes in agriculture, the theoretical, methodological, and practical aspects of risk insurance under state support have not been sufficiently studied, which underscores the relevance and scientific-practical significance of this research article.

Literature Review

The theoretical foundations of institutional research have been developed by G. Becker, V. Bychenkov, T.B. Veblen, W. Hamilton, S.V. Grebennikov, V.V. Zotov, O.V. Inshakov, G.B. Kleiner, D. Commons, O. Conte, N.N. Lebedeva, G.P. Litvintseva, A. Nekipelov, R.M. Nureev, A.N. Oleynik, J. Olson, V.F. Presnyakov, V.O. Rozenhal, K. Savigny, H. Spencer, V.L. Tambovtsev, O. Williamson, T.F. Fayzullin, A.I. Fayzullina, D.P. Frolov, and other classical representatives of economic science.

Methodological research in institutionalism has been presented in the works of A.V. Andreev, M.D. Georgiev, M.M. Georgiev, D.K. Galbraith, S.V. Degtyareva, O.M. Dyushe, S.K. Yeshugova, S.V. Istomin, D.M. Clark, R. Coase, K. Menger, F. Knight, D.R. Pozner, E. Raskov, G. Simon, A.M. Sergeev, O.S. Sukharev, O.V. Fedonin, F. Hayek, A.E. Shastitko, T. Eggertsson, and others.

Using an institutional approach to study various aspects of agricultural development has been done by R.Kh. Adukhov, P.I. Dugin, V.N. Galin, V.I. Gayduk, G.M. Gritsenko, A.P. Zadkov, V.I. Inshakov, M.E. Kadomtseva, L.S. Kazinets, P.D. Kosinsky, V.V. Kossov, B.S. Koshelev, A.V. Krivosheev, I.V. Kurtsev, O.V. Maevsky, A.F. Maksimov, I.V. Palatkin, P.M. Pershukevich,

E.V. Popov, L.R. Popova, E.V. Salalykina, V.F. Stukach, L.V. Tyu, I.G. Ushachev, N.G. Filimonova, D.P. Frolov, V.A. Shabashev, S.V. Sharybar, Yu.I. Schmidt, I.V. Shchetinina, and other agricultural economists.

The methodological problems of forming and developing agricultural insurance have been studied by E.V. Abdrakhimov, M.I. Basakov, V.S. Belykh, O.I. Biryuchyev, D. Bland, K. Burrow, K.S. Vobly, A.A. Gvozdenko, V.N. Dadkov, A.P. Zadkov, A.A. Zernov, A.N. Zubets, M.A. Klimova, S.M. Lapaev, Yu.I. Lini, L.K. Tsikitenkov, A.V. Nikitin, A.M. Onishchenko, L.A. Orlanyuk-Malitskaya, I.V. Orlova, A.P. Pleshkov, V.N. Semenov, A.V. Fedorenko, M.N. Eldiev.

Uzbek scholars and specialists have also published a number of studies in this field, including T. Malikov, O. Olimjonov, H. Sobirov, M. Asqarova, G. Akhunova, X. Boev, T. Baymurotov, O. Jo‘rayev, T. Iminov, M. Mirsodiqov, Y. Tursunov, M. Xodjaeva, A. Shermukhamedov, Sh. Imomov, H. Shennaev, X. Boev, P. Kaziev, B. Xodiev, B. Hamidov, T. Baymuratov, M. Mirsodiqov, B. Ashrafkhonov, R. Khusanov, A. Yadgarov. Despite the important role of the agricultural sector and agricultural insurance in Uzbekistan’s economy, independent scientific research in this area remains limited.

The theoretical and methodological issues of economic risk assessment have been reflected in the works of J.M. Keynes, F. Knight, J. Neumann, O. Morgenstern, J. Schumpeter, and other prominent economists. Although J.M. Keynes did not specifically study risk in his *The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money*, he discussed decision-making under uncertainty, credit risk, and inflation risk. F. Knight examined the relationship between risk, uncertainty, and business profit under perfect and imperfect competition in his work *Risk, Uncertainty, and Profit*. J. Neumann and O. Morgenstern approached the concepts of uncertainty and risk from the perspective of game theory. The well-known Austrian economist J. Schumpeter, in his *Theory of Economic Development*, analyzed factors driving constant changes in economic systems and paid special attention to the classification and grouping of risks based on economic dynamics.

Research on risk management in the CIS countries became especially active at the end of the last century. I.T. Balabanov studied the essence of risk management, methods for reducing risk levels, directions, strategies, and insurance [9]; K.V. Baldin analyzed the methodological, organizational, and technological foundations of management decisions under risk conditions [10]; S.M. Vasin and V.S. Shutov studied entrepreneurial risks, their classification, identification, and analysis methods, and the peculiarities of integrating risks into corporate strategy [12]. Among Uzbek scholars, M. Sharifkhodjaev and Y. Abdullaev researched risk management, types of risk, and methods of managing them [7]; Sh. Zainutdinov and A. Shermukhamedov analyzed risks encountered in management processes and their classification [8]; A. Abdullaev studied the theoretical foundations of organizing farm operations, one of the advanced forms of production [5]; A. Abduganiev researched agriculture and its role, significance, and efficiency in the economy [6].

Analysis and Results: The necessity to improve insurance practices for risk management under conditions of institutional changes in agriculture is reflected in the following points:

Agricultural production, as a specific type of economic activity, is associated with a high level of risks;

In most cases, agricultural enterprises are unable to independently compensate for losses caused by natural disasters or production-related damages;

Insurance protection serves as a guarantee for covering losses associated with adverse events and ensuring the sustainable development of the agricultural sector.

In practice, various strategies for risk management in agriculture have been developed, but agricultural insurance remains an effective tool for protecting against different agricultural risks and unforeseen losses. Agricultural insurance is not only a tested mechanism for managing all types of agricultural risks but also the most optimal way to unify the interests of all participants in the insurance market. Therefore, developing modern models for insuring the agricultural sector requires an innovative approach.

Recently, special attention has been paid by farming households to land use: “When optimizing the land plots of farming households and other agricultural enterprises, their activities over the last three years are thoroughly analyzed. If the size of the agricultural enterprises’ land plots is smaller than the specified limits, they are optimized. Priority is given to multi-sector farms, cotton-textile clusters, exporting and processing enterprises, which have direct investments, good financial status, and agricultural machinery, for the lands returned to the district administration’s reserve” [4].

The expansion of economic reforms in agriculture and the creation of favorable conditions for effective operation of farmers and peasant households can be considered positive. Leasing land to producers of peasant products for a long term based on tenders, considering various factors including farmers’ access to relevant information and machinery, contributes to efficient land use and ultimately increases crop yields.

At the same time, it is necessary to remember that the successful operation of farmers and peasant households is not determined solely by the factors mentioned above. Practical experience shows that compliance with agrotechnical rules alone is insufficient to ensure steady development in the agricultural sector. The yield level and production volumes are heavily influenced by favorable weather conditions, adequate rainfall, and other natural factors.

It is particularly important to emphasize that insurance plays a key role in compensating for losses suffered by agricultural producers, primarily farmers and peasant households, due to natural disasters and other unforeseen events. Insurance is a reliable tool that protects the property interests of all economic entities and the population.

Despite the current high level of scientific and technological development, many countries around the world frequently face problems associated with the intensification of natural, climatic, and economic risks, which increasingly have a global character.

At the same time, analysis of international practice shows that insurance is the most effective method for managing risks to ensure the continuity and financial stability of agricultural production.

The high dependence of agriculture on natural climatic conditions necessitates extensive use of insurance and insurance system capabilities in managing agricultural production risks. Insurance allows effective management of risks associated with the use of new technologies, credit resources, and the sale of agricultural products through exchange systems (spot, forward, futures). High-quality insurance services and relevant government programs enable financial stability for agricultural producers and reduce state budget expenditures aimed at supporting the agricultural sector.

The agricultural insurance market in our country has been operating for more than twenty years to organize compensation for losses suffered by agricultural enterprises, including farmers and peasant households, due to natural disasters and other risks, and to fully meet the demand of agricultural producers for insurance services. However, despite positive developments in protecting the property interests of farmers and peasant households, there remain unresolved

problems, such as: introducing market mechanisms into the agricultural insurance system, insufficient coverage of insurance protection, high loss rates in crop insurance, reliance on traditional principles for insuring agricultural crops, producers’ property, and livestock, insufficient provision of non-traditional insurance services for farmers’ entrepreneurial risks, and others.

To positively resolve these issues, urgent measures are required, including: expanding and improving types of insurance services covering various risks in farmers’ activities; attracting insurance companies of different ownership forms to the agricultural insurance market and fostering healthy competition; encouraging private insurance companies to offer agricultural insurance services; developing new mechanisms for insuring risks in multi-sector farms; improving risk management mechanisms at all levels of sector governance; involving the “Plant Protection Center” in assessing insurance events and determining losses; developing indicators for objective assessment of agricultural risks; expanding public-private partnerships in agricultural insurance; simplifying and ensuring transparency in handling insurance claims; introducing partial return of premiums in case of no insurance event, etc.

Currently, agricultural insurance in our country is developing and improving. The state joint-stock insurance company “UzAgroSUGURTA” provides services for insuring agricultural crops. Operating under the Law “On Insurance Activities,” this company offers about 40 types of insurance services in the field of agricultural insurance.

In 2017, “UzAgroSUGURTA” concluded a total of 3,337.5 thousand insurance contracts. Of these, 53.7 thousand (1.61%) were related to agricultural insurance. The company received insurance premiums of 37.3 billion UZS and accepted insurance liabilities amounting to 1.9 trillion UZS. Within the framework of obligations, compensation of 73.8 billion UZS was paid to agricultural insurance clients. Agricultural risk insurance accounted for 27.8% of the insurance portfolio (Table 1).

Table 1

Indicators of “UzAgroSUGURTA” JSC Agricultural Insurance for 2021–2023

Indicator	Unit	Total	2023	2021	2022	2023
Insurance premiums	million UZS	234081.5	43862.7	67609	71314.0	
Insurance compensations	million UZS	163337.3	8765.0	23441	89864.4	
Insurance liabilities	billion UZS	67458.8	2150.4	2347.390	2532.3	
Number of contracts	thousand	4737.5	42.96	63	68.7	

*Prepared based on the reports of “UzAgroSUGURTA” JSC

In the context of institutional changes in agriculture, the theoretical and methodological basis for studying risk insurance with state support is formed by the concepts of institutional changes in agriculture, agricultural risk management, and improving the system of risk insurance with state support. This requires a deeper study of the methodology and methodological aspects of state-supported agricultural risk insurance.

Although this area has been widely studied by domestic researchers, the liberalization of the economy and accelerated structural reforms demand a new approach to studying risk management in farmers’ activities. The necessity of developing agricultural insurance practice is reflected in:

Agricultural production being a highly risky economic activity;

Most agricultural enterprises being unable to independently compensate for losses caused by natural disasters or production;

Insurance protection serving as a guarantee to cover losses and ensure sustainable agricultural development.

In practice, various risk management strategies have been developed, but agricultural insurance remains an effective tool for protecting against unforeseen losses. It is a tested mechanism for managing all types of agricultural risks and the optimal way to unite all participants in the insurance market. Therefore, developing modern models for agricultural insurance requires an innovative approach.

The goal of the new approach to state-supported agricultural risk insurance is to improve the methodological and scientific foundations for insuring risks under institutional changes and to develop effective mechanisms and measures for utilizing insurance opportunities in agriculture.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks must be accomplished:

Study the institutional approach to state regulation of the economy and theories of institutional changes in agriculture;

Justify the institutional role of farmers and peasant households in agriculture and the necessity of insuring them;

Investigate theoretical foundations of state-supported agricultural risk insurance;

Explore the main principles, forms, and organizational models of state-supported agricultural insurance, as well as development patterns;

Study international experience in agricultural risk insurance;

Analyze institutionalism methodology and technologies for implementing institutional changes in agriculture;

Assess and scientifically study institutional changes in agriculture;

Analyze the foundations of institutional activity, financial bases of institutional agreements, and the efficiency of the institutional environment in agriculture;

Highlight the institutional role and significance of farmers and peasant households in agricultural reforms;

Examine methodological features of providing budget subsidies for agricultural insurance;

Develop methods for assessing the volume and efficiency of state support for agricultural insurance;

Analyze trends in other types of agricultural insurance;

Study international aspects of state-supported agricultural insurance;

Analyze the current practice of insuring farmers and peasant households at the present stage of agricultural insurance development in Uzbekistan;

Provide recommendations for improving the organizational and economic foundations of institutional changes in agriculture;

Develop proposals for improving the scientific-methodological basis of state-supported agricultural risk insurance;

Provide recommendations for improving the organizational foundations of insuring farmers and peasant households;

Develop a strategy for the development of agricultural insurance and substantiate a concept for improving agricultural insurance in Uzbekistan.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Risk management is a crucial task for ensuring the sustainable development of the agricultural sector.

In the context of institutional changes in agriculture, a new approach to the methodology of state-supported agricultural risk insurance allows:

Conceptual and terminological development – A systematic approach enables a new interpretation of the concepts “institutional changes in agriculture” and “state-supported agricultural risk insurance,” and a refined terminological framework is developed.

Scientific analysis of key factors – Factors necessitating a new approach to state-supported agricultural risk insurance in Uzbekistan are scientifically analyzed, and measures for their effective management are substantiated.

Methodology for assessment – A methodology is developed to evaluate the agricultural risk insurance process, taking into account both causal and outcome-based aspects, in order to efficiently utilize the principles, forms, organizational models, and development opportunities of state-supported insurance.

Institutional evaluation and recommendations – The activities of agricultural institutions, the financial basis of institutional agreements, and the effectiveness of the institutional environment are comprehensively assessed using specific coefficients. Systematic research of these factors provides methodological recommendations for agricultural risk insurance.

Development prospects and economic impact – Methodologies are developed to identify priority factors for effectively organizing state-supported risk insurance and to assess its impact on economic growth.

Strategic development and conceptual framework – Based on a new conceptual scheme for analyzing the interrelations of various factors, a strategy for developing agricultural insurance in Uzbekistan is formulated, and the concept for improving agro-insurance is scientifically justified.

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